

Over-the-Air Diagnosis of 1-Bit RIS Based on Amplitude-Only Measurement

Fengchun Zhang, Yifa Li, Gert Pedersen, and Wei Fan

Abstract—Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) have demonstrated their potential to manipulate properties of radio waves for many applications. Over-the-air (OTA) diagnosis of RISs is essential to ensure their proper radiation characteristics. In this work, we propose a novel OTA diagnosis method for 1-bit RIS based on amplitude-only measurements. The proposed algorithm is also experimentally validated with a single-probe setup in an anechoic chamber, where all RIS faulty elements can be correctly detected based on phaseless measurements. The proposed method is experimentally demonstrated to be highly efficient, cost-effective and effective. The proposed method is significant for RIS characterization, as it ensures the optimal performance and reliability of RIS systems across various applications.

Index Terms—reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS), fault diagnosis, over-the-air (OTA), phaseless measurement

I. INTRODUCTION

RECONFIGURABLE intelligent surfaces (RISs), composed of a large-scale discrete set of phase-tunable RIS antenna elements, have great potential to manipulate electromagnetic waves [1], [2]. By controlling its tunable unit cells, an RIS can function as an electromagnetic programmable mirror, reflecting incident electromagnetic waves towards a desired (typically anomalous) direction. Its capability to manipulate radio waves has been experimentally demonstrated for various applications, such as electronic beam-steering [3], [4], programmable-metasurface-stirred reverberation chamber [5], metasurface-assisted IoT communications [6], coverage enhancement in 5G commercial mobile networks [7], performance improvements and increased design flexibility in non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) networks [8], spectrum- and energy-efficient enhancements in wireless communication [9], and more [10], [11]. Passive RIS, reflecting signals without amplification, has attracted great interest from both industry and academia due to its low-cost design and no need for additional power. For cost-saving and simplicity, passive RIS with a low-bit phase shifter design (e.g., enabled by one or multiple PIN diodes per RIS element) has been the most popular scheme.

Fengchun Zhang, Yifa Li, and Gert Pedersen are with the Antennas, Propagation and Millimeter-wave Systems section at the Department of Electronic Systems, Aalborg University, Denmark.

Wei Fan is with the National Mobile Communications Research Laboratory at the School of Information Science and Engineering, Southeast University, and also with Purple Mountain Laboratories, China (Corresponding author: Wei Fan, email: weifan@seu.edu.cn)

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RIS characterization is essential to ensure its desired radiation performance in the deployment scenarios. State-of-the-art works have been mainly focused on RIS array far-field beam-steering and near-field power focusing measurements [3]. Recently, diagnosis and calibration of RIS array has been discussed [12]–[14]. Indeed, RIS element-level characterization is important since this knowledge can be of importance for RIS in various applications. Calibration and diagnosis of multi-antenna systems (e.g. phased arrays, plane wave generator (PWG), etc.) has been a long-standing research topic [15], [16]. However, RIS characterization is more challenging due to the higher likelihood of manufacturing defects or errors resulting from its cost-effective design, large-scale configurations, lack of access port for signaling, limited RIS phase tuning, and little or no amplitude control capability. Over-the-air (OTA) testing, which uses radio wave to carry testing signal between device under test (DUT) to a probe antenna (connected to the instruments), is the only viable solution for RIS testing.

The “park and probe” method [17], widely adopted in the industry for phased array calibration, can be employed for RIS diagnosis in principle. As illustrated in Fig. 1, a probe antenna connected to the vector network analyzer (VNA), can be moved and aligned to illuminate each RIS element and measure the reflection coefficient S_{11} sequentially. For each aligned RIS element, we can check whether its phase and amplitude tuning works as expected. This approach is quite useful for design and development of RIS as well as preliminary validation of the RIS unit cell functionality. However, it requires complex signal measurement, and the mechanical movement of the scanner, along with the precise alignment between each individual RIS element and the probe antenna, can be challenging. These challenges are particularly pronounced for large-scale RIS configurations and higher frequency bands. The former results in long measurement times, while the later requires extremely precise alignment due to the smaller unit size, further complicating the process and increasing sensitive to alignment uncertainties. Unlike the “on-off” mode used in the “park and probe” method for phased array calibration, passive RIS typically do not support individual element “on-off” operation. As a result, coupling among RIS elements will affect the RIS diagnosis results. It also requires knowledge of the RIS configuration, which might be not accessible in practice. Hence, the “park and probe” method is problematic for RIS diagnosis. In our previous work [14], an OTA diagnosis method for 1-bit RIS based on complex signal measurement was proposed. This solution was experimentally demonstrated to be highly effective and to work well in a compact setup.

Fig. 1. An illustration of the "Park and Probe" scheme for RIS diagnosis based on reflection coefficient measurement.

However, phase measurement might be unavailable, inaccurate and expensive in some cases, such as during on-site measurements, or at mmWave and higher frequencies, or when only amplitude-only measurement equipment like spectrum analyzers is available, ect [15], [16], [18]–[20]. Phaseless measurement, on the other hand, allows cheaper and more flexible measurement setups. The rotating element field vector (REV) method is a classic phaseless measurement technique for phased array calibration [15], [16]. The REV method requires tuning phase of each phased array element or each RIS unit from 0° to 360° , with at least 3 phase states (e.g., 0° , 90° and 180°), as discussed in [15], [16]. This implies that at least 2-bit phase shifters are required for the RIS under test. Thus, the REV method is not applicable for diagnosing RISs with 1-bit phase shifters. RIS diagnosis based on amplitude-only method is highly valuable in practice. However, it has not been addressed and remains an open challenge in the literature, to our best knowledge.

In this work, a novel OTA diagnosis algorithm based on phaseless measurement is proposed to detect faulty phase shifters in passive 1-bit RIS systems. The solution is simple, since it only requires phase inversion operation for each RIS element, which can be implemented by 1-bit phase shifts in the RIS. It is cost-effective, as the diagnosis can be performed in the mid-field rather than the far-field of the RIS under test, allowing the use of a compact chamber. It is flexible, as the group size in the diagnosis process can be adjusted to balance diagnostic accuracy and speed. It is versatile, applicable to RISs of any size and configurations. It is also highly time-efficient, requiring a minimum of $(1 + 3/2N)$ power measurements to diagnose an N -element RIS without any mechanical movement.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II derives and explains the proposed method, Section III describes the validation measurement campaign and discusses the results, and Section IV concludes the work.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

A. Proposed Phaseless Diagnosis method

1) *Phase inversion operation of RIS elements*: Assuming an N -unit RIS, we can in principle use the phase inverse method

to diagnose the phase shifters of RIS units as derived below.

For diagnosing the n -th phase shifter, we first set 0° to all RIS units and the complex signal received by the Rx can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} y_{n,1} &= E_n + \sum_{q \neq n} E_q \\ &= E_n + \tilde{E}_n, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where E_n denotes the complex signal reflected by the n -th RIS unit, while \tilde{E}_n represents the composite complex signal reflected by the remaining RIS units. The subscript i of $y_{n,i}$ denotes the i -th phase setting. The power of $y_{n,1}$ is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{n,1} &= y_{n,1} \cdot y_{n,1}^* = (E_n + \tilde{E}_n) \cdot (E_n^* + \tilde{E}_n^*) \\ &= |E_n|^2 + |\tilde{E}_n|^2 + 2|E_n| \cdot |\tilde{E}_n| \cos \tilde{\phi}_{n,n}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\tilde{\phi}_{n,n} = \angle E_n - \angle \tilde{E}_n$ is the phase difference between E_n and \tilde{E}_n .

We can then set the phase of the n -th RIS unit to 180° while keeping the phases of the remaining RIS units to 0° , which results in the signal received by the Rx expressed as:

$$y_{n,2} = E_n \cdot e^{j\theta_n} + \tilde{E}_n, \quad (3)$$

where θ_n stands for the actual phase shift implemented to the n -th RIS unit. Similarly, the power of $y_{n,2}$ is then given as:

$$p_{n,2} = |E_n|^2 + |\tilde{E}_n|^2 + 2|E_n| \cdot |\tilde{E}_n| \cos(\tilde{\phi}_{n,n} + \theta_n). \quad (4)$$

The power deviation due to the phase adjustment for the n -th RIS unit can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta p_{n,1} &= |p_{n,1} - p_{n,2}| \\ &= 4|E_n| \cdot |\tilde{E}_n| \cdot \left| \sin \frac{\theta_n}{2} \right| \cdot \left| \sin \frac{2\tilde{\phi}_{n,n} + \theta_n}{2} \right|. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Below, we add a superscribe to $\Delta p_{n,1}$ to indicate whether the phase shifter is working or not. More specifically, the superscribe setting to 1, i.e., $\Delta p_{n,1}^1$, is used to indicate the working case and setting to 0, i.e., $\Delta p_{n,1}^0$, is used to indicate the malfunctioning case.

When the phase shifter of the n -th RIS is well functioning, i.e., achieving the actual phase shift $\theta_n = \pi$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta p_{n,1}^1 &= 4|E_n| \cdot \left| \sin \frac{\pi}{2} \right| \cdot \left| |\tilde{E}_n| \cdot \sin \frac{2\tilde{\phi}_{n,n} + \pi}{2} \right| \\ &= 4|E_n| \cdot |\tilde{E}_n| \cdot |\cos \tilde{\phi}_{n,n}| \\ &= 4 \cdot \langle E_n, \tilde{E}_n \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\langle a, b \rangle$ represents the inner product of two Euclidean vectors. The above equation reveals that $\Delta p_{n,1}^1$ is determined by four times of the inner product of E_n and \tilde{E}_n . It is noted that the field vectors E_n and \tilde{E}_n are Euclidean vectors, whose magnitude is represented by their length, and their direction is indicated by their phase. When the absolute value of the phase difference between two vectors is 90° , the two vectors are perpendicular to each other, resulting in a zero inner product of the two vectors.

In the contrast, if this phase shifter malfunctions, i.e., the actual phase shift $\theta_n = 0$, we have

$$\Delta p_{n,1}^0 = 0. \quad (7)$$

However, $\Delta p_{n,1}^0 = 0$ can never be achieved in practice, due to noises and uncertainties of the phase shifters in the measurements. In order to well distinguish the faulty phase shifter RIS units from the fault-free ones, it is desirable to have $\Delta p_{m_1,1} \gg \Delta p_{m_0,1}$ with m_1 and m_0 representing the indexes of the fault-free and faulty units, respectively. Moreover, the detection becomes more challenging, when E_n and \tilde{E}_n in (6) are close to perpendicular to each other, resulting in $\Delta p_{n,1}^1 \approx 0$ even when this phase shift is well functioning. This can lead to the false detection of the fault-free RIS units.

2) *Grouping operation of RIS elements*: To tackle the false detection issue, we can diagnose RIS units group by group. For simplicity, we assume each group composed of two RIS units. Without loss of generality, we suppose that the n -th and the $(n+1)$ -th RIS units compose a group. We can further decompose \tilde{E}_n as:

$$\tilde{E}_n = E_{n+1} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1}, \quad (8)$$

with $\tilde{E}_{n,n+1}$ representing the composite complex signal excluding signals attributed by the n -th and the $(n+1)$ -th RIS units. The power deviation $\Delta p_{n,1}^1$ in (6) can be rewritten as:

$$\Delta p_{n,1}^1 = 4 \cdot \langle E_n, E_{n+1} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle. \quad (9)$$

To enlarge the power gap of the Δp_n for the fault-free units and the malfunctioning units, we can collect two more measurements at the Rx denoted by $y_{n,3}$ and $y_{n,4}$. The signal $y_{n,3}$ is measured by setting 180° for the $(n+1)$ -th RIS unit and 0° for the other RIS units, whereas the signal $y_{n,4}$ is measured by setting 180° for both the n -th and the $(n+1)$ -th RIS units, and 0° for the other RIS units. We thereby have:

$$y_{n,3} = E_n + E_{n+1} \cdot e^{j\theta_{n+1}} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1}, \quad (10)$$

and

$$y_{n,4} = E_n \cdot e^{j\theta_n} + E_{n+1} \cdot e^{j\theta_{n+1}} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1}. \quad (11)$$

Similar to the derivation of $\Delta p_{n,1}$, the difference between these two received power signals can be calculated. We have

$$\Delta p_{n,2}^0 = 0 \quad (12)$$

and

$$\Delta p_{n,2}^1 = 4 \cdot \langle E_n, E_{n+1} e^{j\theta_{n+1}} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle. \quad (13)$$

By adding $\Delta p_{n,1}$ and $\Delta p_{n,2}$, the resulting power deviation for the n -th RIS unit can be given as:

$$\Delta p_n = \Delta p_{n,1} + \Delta p_{n,2}. \quad (14)$$

For the n -th phase shifter malfunctioning case, we have

$$\Delta p_n^0 = \Delta p_{n,1}^0 + \Delta p_{n,2}^0 = 0, \quad (15)$$

according to (7) and (12).

While for the n -th phase shifter well functioning case, the power deviation can be derived based on (6) and (13), as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta p_n^1 &= \Delta p_{n,1}^1 + \Delta p_{n,2}^1 \\ &= 4 \cdot \left\{ \langle E_n, E_{n+1} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \langle E_n, E_{n+1} e^{j\theta_{n+1}} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Fig. 2. Illustration of inner product of (a) $\langle E_n, E_{n+1} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle$ and (b) $\langle E_n, -E_{n+1} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle$.

If the phase shifter of the $(n+1)$ -th RIS is malfunctioning, i.e., $\theta_{n+1} = 0$, (16) becomes

$$\Delta p_n^1 = 8 \cdot \langle E_n, E_{n+1} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle. \quad (17)$$

Otherwise,

$$\Delta p_n^1 = 4 \left\{ \langle E_n, E_{n+1} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle + \langle E_n, -E_{n+1} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle \right\}. \quad (18)$$

An example of the inner products of $\langle E_n, E_{n+1} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle$ and $\langle E_n, -E_{n+1} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle$ are illustrated in Fig. 2 (a) and (b), respectively. It can be observed that we have $E_n \perp (E_{n+1} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1})$ in Fig. 2 (a), leading to the inner product of these two vectors i.e., $\Delta p_{n,1}^1$ becomes 0. By shifting the phase of E_{n+1} 180° as shown in Fig. 2 (b), the resulting composite vector $(-E_{n+1} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1})$ is not perpendicular to E_n , implying $\Delta p_{n,2}^1 > 0$. Thus, the probability of both $E_n \perp E_{n+1}$ and $E_n \perp \tilde{E}_n$ is smaller than the probability of $E_n \perp \tilde{E}_n$. Hence, group-based phase tuning leading to Δp_n defined in (14), is more robust than the element-based phase tuning leading to $\Delta p_{n,1}$ for detecting malfunctioning phase shifters of RIS units.

Similarly, we can extract the power deviation caused by the phase adjustment for the $(n+1)$ -th RIS unit by using the four power data $p_{n,1}$, $p_{n,2}$, $p_{n,3}$ and $p_{n,4}$. By analogy, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta p_{n+1,1}^1 &= |p_{n,1} - p_{n,3}| \\ &= 4 \cdot \langle E_{n+1}, E_n + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta p_{n+1,2}^1 &= |p_{n,2} - p_{n,4}| \\ &= 4 \cdot \langle E_{n+1}, E_n e^{j\theta_n} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta p_{n+1}^1 &= \Delta p_{n+1,1}^1 + \Delta p_{n+1,2}^1 \\ &= 4 \cdot \left\{ \langle E_{n+1}, E_n + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \langle E_{n+1}, E_n e^{j\theta_n} + \tilde{E}_{n,n+1} \rangle \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

A similar discussion regarding Δp_n^1 can be applied to Δp_{n+1}^1 . Therefore, the combination of the grouping operation and the phase inversion operation of RIS elements can effectively diagnose the faulty RIS elements using phaseless measurements.

The diagnosis procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1. It is noted that the N RIS elements are divided into $Q = N/2$ groups with each group containing 2 units, where the RIS units within the q -th group are indexed as q_1 and q_2 respectively.

Algorithm 1 Diagnosis procedure

- 1: Divide the N RIS elements into $Q = N/2$ groups with each group containing 2 RIS units;
 - 2: Set the phases of all RIS elements to 0° and measure the power signal recorded at the Rx antenna port denoted by p_0 ;
 - 3: **for** $q = 1$ to Q **do**
 - 4: Assign the phase combinations $\{180^\circ, 0^\circ\}$, $\{0^\circ, 180^\circ\}$ and $\{180^\circ, 180^\circ\}$ to the RIS elements within the group, while fixing the phases of the remaining RIS elements to 0° . For each phase setting, measure the power signals recorded at the Rx antenna port denoted as $p_{q,2}$, $p_{q,3}$ and $p_{q,4}$ respectively;
 - 5: Calculate the power deviation for the q_1 -th RIS $\Delta p_{q_1} = |p_0 - p_{q,2}| + |p_{q,3} - p_{q,4}|$;
 - 6: Calculate the power deviation for the q_2 -th RIS $\Delta p_{q_2} = |p_0 - p_{q,3}| + |p_{q,2} - p_{q,4}|$;
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: Compare Δp_n among RIS elements and detect the faulty element(s).
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B. Discussion

In principle, the RIS units can be divided into groups of arbitrary size L , where $L \geq 2$. Assume the RIS units are equally divided to Q groups, with each group containing $L = N/Q$ units. When the phase shifter of the l -th RIS unit in the q -th group malfunctions, the power deviation term be derived analogously to (15) as

$$\Delta p_{q_l}^0 = 0. \quad (22)$$

In contrast, when the l -th RIS unit in the q -th group functions properly, the resulting power deviation term in (18) can be expressed as:

$$\Delta p_{q_l}^1 = 4 \left\{ (L-1) \langle E_{q_l}, \tilde{E}_{q_l} \rangle + \sum_{i \neq q_l, i \in [q_1, \dots, q_L]} \langle E_{q_l}, E_i e^{j\theta_i} + \tilde{E}_{q_l, i} \rangle \right\}. \quad (23)$$

The above equation indicates that $\Delta p_{q_l}^1$ increases monotonically with the group size L , implying that a larger group size results in a greater power gap between $\Delta p_{q_l}^1$ and $\Delta p_{q_l}^0$, thereby enabling more accurate detection of RIS phase shifter faults.

However, the higher detection accuracy comes at the cost of an increased number of measurements and longer measurement time. As explained above, each RIS unit in a group must adjust its phase to two states (i.e., 0° and 180°), resulting in 2^L possible phase setting combinations for L units in the group. Therefore, for a group with L units, $(2^L - 1)$ additional power measurements are required. To diagnose an N -unit RIS with

Fig. 3. A photo of the measurement setup for RIS diagnosis.

a group size of L , the total number of measurements can be calculated as:

$$M = (2^L - 1) \cdot N/L + 1. \quad (24)$$

as a summary, a larger group size, that is, each group containing more units, generally leads to a larger power gap between the fault-free units and the malfunctioning unit(s), thereby making the diagnosis more robust. However, the cost is a larger number of measurements and a longer diagnosis time.

III. MEASUREMENT VALIDATION

A. Measurement Setup

The validation measurement was carried out in a single-probe setup in an anechoic chamber, as shown in Fig. 3. Note that the measurement setup has been reported in [3], [14].

- A RIS with a 10×10 rectangular lattice configuration, i.e., consisting of 100 units, was used as the DUT. Each unit has a 2-bit resolution for phase shifting and operates at the frequency band from 3.4 GHz to 3.6 GHz. Each individual unit is designed with solid-state-control devices (PIN diodes) that allow for electrical phase tuning of the radio waves impinging on each RIS unit. To control the working status of the PIN diodes and dynamically reconfigure the phase shift of each element, a logic circuit control board with a J30J-15ZKP port is used. The RIS is fabricated using multi-layer printed circuit board (PCB) technology, which allows for precise manufacturing of the panel's intricate design. The RIS controller is an FPGA-based integrated circuit board, which provides a flexible and efficient way of controlling the RIS.
- A feeding antenna illuminated the RIS from a distance of 50 cm to the RIS center, with an incident angle of 50° off the boresight direction of the RIS.
- A probe antenna on the multi-probe ring in the boresight direction of the RIS was employed as the Rx antenna.
- A VNA measured the S21 between the feeding and probe antenna ports. The frequency was set to 3.5 GHz.

- A PC automated the RIS phase tuning, VNA operations, and data saving processes. Note that the entire procedure was fully automated, supporting real-time RIS diagnosis.

It is noted that the proposed diagnosis method, in principle, works in any shielded chamber environment. Compared to diagnosing RISs in an anechoic chamber, diagnosing RISs in a non-anechoic chamber environment introduces challenges due to the multi-path fading effect. This effect causes Δp_n for the fault-free phase shifters of the RIS units to fluctuate within a larger range, degrading diagnosis accuracy. Therefore, RIS diagnosis is typically performed in an anechoic chamber to exclude external interference and eliminate the impact of multipath.

B. Measurement Procedure

To balance between the diagnosis accuracy and measurement efficiency, the RIS units were divided into groups, with each containing 2 units in our measurement. Initially, the phase shifters were set to 0° for all RIS elements. To detect the first two RIS elements (i.e., the elements with index 1 and 2), the phase shifters of these two elements were configured to $(0^\circ, 180^\circ)$, $(180^\circ, 0^\circ)$, and $(180^\circ, 180^\circ)$ sequentially, while the phase shifts for the remaining RIS elements were kept unchanged at 0° . S21 between the feeding and probe antenna ports was measured for each phase shift setting on RIS elements. That is, we collected 4 measurements, corresponding to the four phase states $(0^\circ, 0^\circ)$, $(0^\circ, 180^\circ)$, $(180^\circ, 0^\circ)$, and $(180^\circ, 180^\circ)$, to detect the two RIS units in the first group. The same procedure was repeated for other groups of RIS units. Consequently, a total of 151 (i.e., $1+3 \times 100/2$) measurements were conducted throughout the entire diagnosis procedure.

C. Measurement Campaign

It is worth noting that in principle, the proposed algorithm can diagnose a RIS with any number of failure elements located anywhere, although typically only few elements might be broken in practice. To validate the proposed diagnosis method, four different scenarios of RIS faults were used. These scenarios were designed to test the method's effectiveness and robustness, as faulty elements in practical applications can be arbitrary in number and location. The following are the details of the four representative testing cases used for this validation:

- 1) One-faulty-element case: emulating malfunction of an edge RIS element with index 8.
- 2) One-faulty-element case: emulating malfunction of a non-edge RIS element with index 15.
- 3) Two-faulty-element case: emulating malfunctions at adjacent RIS elements with indexes 65 and 66, positioned around the RIS center.
- 4) Four-faulty-element case: emulating malfunctions at multiple elements with indexes 8, 15, 65, and 66.

Note that, for the faulty RIS elements, the phase of the faulty element was kept at 0° during the diagnosis procedure to replicate the malfunctioning of the phase shifter. For each testing case, the above discussed measurement procedure was repeated for all RIS elements. Therefore we recorded a total

Fig. 4. Diagnosis results for the four faulty scenarios.

of 4×151 S21 measurements (though only the magnitudes of S21 were used in the algorithm), and the entire measurement campaign was automated.

D. Measurement Results

The measurement results for the four cases are shown in Fig. 4. We can clearly observe that the proposed method can effectively detect the faulty RIS elements. The measured results demonstrate that the proposed method is capable of detecting arbitrary number of faulty RIS elements at arbitrary locations. The gap between the working RIS elements and faulty RIS elements is 13.2 dB, 17.1 dB, 14.7 dB and 13.8 dB for the first, second, third and fourth case, respectively. As discussed, we can increase the grouping size of RIS elements with the proposed method to enlarge the gap. However, this comes at the cost of longer measurement time.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes and experimentally validates a novel automated method for OTA diagnosis of RISs based solely on amplitude measurements. It focuses on diagnosing RISs equipped with 1-bit phase shifters. The proposed method is highly valuable for RIS diagnosis as it only requires phaseless measurements and operates effectively in a cost-effective compact antenna measurement setup. Demonstrations show that measurement can be performed with a feed antenna and probe antenna in the near-field of the RIS. The gap between the faulty and working RIS elements is larger than 13 dB for all testing cases, demonstrating its effectiveness in practical setups. Moreover, the measurement campaign can be conducted in a fully automated and time-efficient manner, without any mechanical movement. Finally, the proposed phaseless solution is a generic OTA diagnosis solution for 1-bit RIS (i.e. with phase setting of 0° and 180° only). It is also applicable to RISs of large-scale configurations, making it promising for

future applications. Diagnosing the phase shifters of higher-bit RISs will be addressed in future research.

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